

INTENTION TO STAY: ASSESSING THE INTERPLAY OF JOB SATISFACTION, WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND WORK ENGAGEMENT AMONG FACULTY IN A FAITH-BASED INSTITUTION

April Khay S. Vacalares and Judith C. Chavez

Lourdes College, Cagayan de Oro, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11259282>

ABSTRACT

Understanding the details of the faculty's factors in the school is of prime importance to retain them longer in the institution. This study examined the factors influencing faculty members' intention to stay in a faith-based institution in Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines. Using a quantitative descriptive-correlational approach with 100 participants, the study utilized questionnaires from Mallillin, (2021), Marmol (2019), Kuok (2022), and Škerháková, et al. (2022) which were modified to suit the context of the study. To ascertain the profile of the study, descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency, percentage, and standard deviation were utilized. ANOVA was used to test the difference with the length of service and a T-test was employed for the differentiating variables of age, marital, and employment status. Regression analysis was employed to determine if job satisfaction, work-life balance, and work engagement significantly influenced the participants' intention to stay. The findings reveal participants' moderate satisfaction levels regarding compensation and benefits while showcasing high levels of satisfaction in the work environment, work-life- balance, and engagement. Notably, the study highlighted moderate physical engagement with high levels of cognitive and emotional engagement among the teachers. Demographic factors of age, marital status, employment status, and length of service are significant sources of variation in their intention to stay. Regression analysis further indicates that the whole model is significant showing that job satisfaction, work-life balance, and work engagement significantly influenced the participants' intention to stay. However, when taken singly, the variables of work engagement and job satisfaction have a significant influence on their intention to stay with work engagement having the highest influence. The findings emphasize the importance of fostering a positive work environment, promoting work-life balance, and enhancing cognitive and emotional engagement to increase the teachers' intention rate.

The study suggests an exploration on the impact of leadership and well-being on faculty retention.

Keywords: *Faculty's Intention to Stay, Job Satisfaction, Work-life balance, and Work Engagement*

INTRODUCTION

Faculty members are essential to a school since they are the backbone of the learning process, contributing significantly to the institution's success in various ways. They impart knowledge and play critical roles in research, mentorship, and shaping the academic and intellectual environment. Furthermore, faculty members facilitate student learning, develop course curricula, design syllabi, select materials, and create assessments. They provide feedback, mentor students, and contribute to knowledge advancement and they also offer academic advice, career guidance, and contribute to the academic community through committee work and administrative roles (Mesha, 2023).

There are several reasons why school faculty members might choose to resign. Institutional, personal, and professional circumstances often play a significant role in an individual's decision to leave (Salinas et.al., 2020). Faculty retention is influenced by various factors such as effective development programs, promotion opportunities, academic freedom, organizational culture, work climate, flexibility, peer support, financial support, and facilities (Sadagheyani et al., 2022). Some studies validate factors for retaining faculty members' various motivations and retention mechanisms, including salary increases, non-monetary incentives, a friendly atmosphere, overseas conference attendance, community outreach, and academic promotions (Abalorio, 2022).

However, universities worldwide are confronted with issues with turnover rates. Ochoa (2023) cited the challenge of Addis Ababa University in retaining high-caliber academic staff, with an average retention period of 4.9 years posing urgent action needed to balance faculty outflow. Another study by Ramasamy & Abdullah (2017) conducted with five Malaysian private universities identified seven key factors contributing to faculty turnover, including employer image, external job opportunities, social media bullying, and unfair compensation. Ibrahim (2021) further revealed that poor working conditions, including the environment, workload, and hours, significantly impact faculty performance in higher education institutes, affecting their psychological well-being.

Moreover, Sedillo and Chavez's (2021) study analyzed faculty turnover intentions in private higher education institutions in Davao City. The study found that 21% of the variance is attributed to satisfaction, emotional competence, and engagement. Faculty members demonstrated emotional competence, expressed satisfaction, and yet harbored doubts about leaving.

Faculty turnover is also a phenomenon in most of the Philippine schools specifically in the study's context. With the mushrooming of local colleges and universities, several teachers opted for these institutions due to the wide disparity of financial gains; hence, the researcher is propelled to conduct this empirical investigation to identify the factors that influence the participants' intention to stay.

Imperative questions are, therefore, likely to arise: Does job satisfaction make them stay? Is it about work-life balance? If teachers are actively engaged in school, will they stay? These questions are worth reflecting on for the school leaders to consider as they draft their faculty retention strategies. Studies are needed to examine the faculty's intention to stay in the said institution both in Integrated Basic Education Department (IBED) and Higher Education Department (HED), especially during the new normal. This study may provide valuable input to the school administration as they draft their faculty development plan. Thus, this study explores the influence of job commitment, job satisfaction, and work engagement on teachers' intentions to stay in one of the faith-based institutions in Cagayan de Oro City.

Framework

This study presupposes that job satisfaction, work-life balance, and work engagement influence the faculty's intention to stay in the school. The higher their job satisfaction, work engagement, and work-life balance, the more likely, teachers stay longer in the organization. This study is anchored on the theoretical framework of Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, highlighting the role of motivators (e.g., intrinsic rewards like recognition and responsibility) and hygiene factors (e.g., extrinsic factors such as compensation and work conditions) in shaping job satisfaction and overall contentment (Rokeman et. al., 2023). Additionally, the Job Characteristics Model by Hackman and Oldham (Pikl, L. (2023), underscores the significance of a positive work environment, emphasizing aspects like skill variety, task identity, autonomy, and feedback, which contribute to higher job satisfaction and motivation, thereby, influencing employees' intentions to stay. Complementing this is the Role Theory's exploration of work-life balance and its impact on well-being and commitment, with organizations promoting this balance experiencing enhanced retention rates (Joshi, 2024). Moreover, Lei & Suntrayuth (2023) posit the Job Demands-Resources Model that clarifies how work engagement, characterized by enthusiasm and dedication, is fostered by adequate job resources and balanced against job demands.

Furthermore, Pham et. al., (2023) analyzed through Social Exchange Theory, shed light on how rational decisions based on costs and benefits within social relationships, including employment status, tenure, age, and civil status, influence employees' perceptions and commitment to their roles in the school ultimately affecting their intention to stay. The study is also anchored in the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), a well-known social psychological theory developed by Icek Ajzen (Qin & Tao, 2021). The TPB is widely used to understand and predict human behavior, including behavioral intentions. The theory posits that behavioral intentions are key predictors of actual behavior (Costan et al., 2022). As applied in the study, the concept of intention to stay, as described by

Alghamdi (2021), is an important component that represents an employee's disposition and strategies to maintain their current job with their employer. The significance of this concept is underscored by Lee et al. (2022) in their efforts to identify and anticipate elements crucial to employee retention. Various theoretical frameworks offer valuable insights into the complexities of the intention to remain, each providing a unique perspective on the factors influencing an employee's decision to continue working for a specific organization (Carmine & De Marchi, 2023).

Moreover, Shanock et al. (2019) stated that the framework of organizational support theory offers an extensive and empirically verified explanation of how employees' perceptions of treatment and socioemotional contentment impact their intentions to stay employed. With its emphasis on the importance of using reliable metrics to understand and quantify the intention to stay, this approach presents an interesting social exchange perspective on employee retention management (Naz et al., 2020). By integrating known theoretical frameworks with predictive variables, researchers and practitioners can gain a significant understanding of the challenges involved in managing employees (Manalo et al., 2024). This, in turn, can help develop methods that effectively enhance employee retention (Krishna et al., 2022).

In this study, the researcher identified compensation, benefits, and work environment as measures of job satisfaction as espoused by Mabaso and Dlamini (2021). Joanna (2020) states that financial and economic factors significantly affect job satisfaction across every profession. Workers value fair compensation for their work at the most fundamental level, based on their abilities, contributions, and effort (Gerhart & Fang, 2023). Receiving a regular salary is a tangible reward for putting in effort. According to Murtiningsih (2020), competitive pay scales positively indicate an employee's abilities and background. Such validation (Malinao & Agustin, 2023) deeply contributes to satisfaction and loyalty. In addition to being equitable, higher-than-average industry pay enables employees to better support their desired lifestyles by covering costs for necessities, savings objectives, leisure activities, and even status items (Roach et al., 2019). Brown et al. (2019), postulates that attaining financial objectives creates great satisfaction. Nonetheless, lower pay rates over time indicate undervalued work and decreased morale (Santoro et al., 2021). Conway, S. (2023) claimed that when wages freeze, employees get discouraged despite increasing credentials and performance contributions and are more likely to look outside their organization for better opportunities.

In brief, job satisfaction as a central construct represents the overall contentment and fulfillment that faculty members derive from their roles (Khosro & Raza, 2023). Espinosa (2024), encompasses multiple dimensions of compensation and benefits that reflect faculty perceptions of the adequacy and fairness of their salary and benefits. The work environment includes the workplace's physical, cultural, and social aspects contributing to overall satisfaction (Becaro et. al., 2023). Relationship with supervisors and colleagues assesses the quality of interpersonal relationships with immediate supervisors and colleagues, emphasizing communication, collaboration, and support (Ji & Jan 2020). Management style continuously evaluates satisfaction with the leadership and management approach within the institution (Arcilla, 2020).

Furthermore, work-life balance is another variable premised to influence faculty's intention to stay. Marmol (2019) states that balance is essential for an enjoyable, successful, and stress-free life. It is an important element in the life of a teacher, which is one of the most stressful, demanding, and challenging careers in any country (Marmol, 2019). Teachers' work-life balance means achieving an optimum balance between their personal and professional lives (Odisa, 2022). Santiago (2023) further espoused that work-life balance is paramount for educational institutions' sustained success and vitality. A well-established work-life balance positively influences faculty retention through various mechanisms (Okiko, L., 2020).

Another variable assumed to have a link to faculty's intention to stay is work engagement. It is a positive, fulfilling state of mind that encompasses physical, cognitive, and emotional aspects of one's work experience (Turner & Turner, 2020). Physical engagement enhances faculty members' ability to manage academic demands, reduces burnout, and increases retention as they feel energized and healthy (Alvarenga, 2020). Meanwhile, cognitive engagement in faculty leads to increased job satisfaction, and retention, as faculty members feel strongly connected to their work's intellectual aspects (Artates, J., 2023). Likewise, emotional engagement significantly influences faculty retention, as positive connections foster a sense of belonging and contribute to a supportive work environment (Sanchez, 2022).

In addition, demographic variables such as employment status, years in service, age, and civil status have a bearing on faculty retention. Aboramadan, Albashiti, Alharazin, and Dahleez (2020) espoused that faculty members exhibit higher commitment and engagement due to their roles, career advancement opportunities, and institutional involvement. Long-serving faculty members may experience increased institutional commitment, but they may also experience burnout or dissatisfaction if not adequately supported or recognized (Boon et al., 2020). Faculty members' expectations and priorities according to Palmer et al. (2020) vary across age groups, with younger faculty seeking growth opportunities and a dynamic work environment and older faculty valuing stability and legacy-making.

Career stage can influence faculty retention, with early-career faculty exploring opportunities, mid-career faculty seeking challenges, and late-career faculty considering retirement plans (Jung, J., 2021). Faculty members with family commitments often prioritize work-life balance and seek institutions with family-friendly policies, which are more likely to retain them (Okiko, L., 2020). Civil status impacts faculty social support networks, with a supportive institutional environment that accommodates the needs of single and married faculty members contributing to retention (Abella, 2020). Figure 1 illustrates the interplay of variables in the study with job satisfaction, work-life balance, work engagement, and personal demographics as the independent variables theorized to influence faculty's intention to stay which is the dependent variable in the study.

Figure 1: Schematic Presentation of the Study

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the factors influencing employees' intention to stay. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the participants' assessment of job satisfaction in terms of:
 - 1.1 Compensation and Benefits; and
 - 1.2 Work Environment?
2. What is the participants' level of work-life balance?
3. What is the participants' assessment of their work engagement in terms of:
 - 3.1 Physical;
 - 3.2 Cognitive; and
 - 3.3 Emotional aspects?
4. What is the participants' level of intention to stay with the organization?
5. Do the participants' intention to stay significantly differ according to:
 - 5.1 Age;
 - 5.2 Civil Status;
 - 5.3 Employment Status; and
 - 5.4 Length of Service?
6. Do the participants' job satisfaction, work-life balance, and work engagement significantly influence their intentions to stay?

METHODOLOGY

This study used a quantitative descriptive-correlational research approach. The research participants in this study involved 100 faculty members in a faith-based institution in Cagayan de Oro City, Northern Mindanao, for School Year 2023-2024. The study was conducted on-site and the researcher used the following statistical tools: descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency, percentage, and standard deviation were used to establish the profile of the study; analysis of variance and t-test were also utilized to determine the significant difference of their intention to stay when grouped according to their demographics; and regression analysis was employed to ascertain if job satisfaction, work-life balance, and work engagement influence their intention to stay.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows that the majority of faculty members (70%) are between 25-34 years old, 10% are 35-44 years old, 16% are 45-64 years old, and Only 4% are 65 years old or above. This indicates that the faculty is a relatively young population, with 70 percent under 35. Regarding civil status, 70 percent of faculty members are single while some are married. The high percentage of single faculty (70%) suggests the institution may want to consider benefits and policies that support these demographics such as tuition discounts for siblings.

Table 1

Distribution of Personal Demographics of Participants' (Age, Civil status, Employment Status, and Number of Years)

<i>Age</i>	Frequency	Percentage
25 - 34 years old	70	70.0
35 - 44 years old	10	10.0
45 - 64 years old	16	16.0
65 years old and above	4	4.0
Total	100	100.0
<i>Civil Status</i>		
Single	70	70.0
Married	30	30.0
Total	100	100.0
<i>Employment Status</i>		
Regular	57	57.0
Probationary	43	43.0
Total	100	100.0
<i>Number of years</i>		
0-3 years	47	47.0
4-8 years	26	26.0
9-15 years	11	11.0
Over 16 years	16	16.0
Total	100	100.0

For employment status, 57 percent of faculty members have regular employment status as compared with 43 percent who are on probationary status. With over 40% on probationary status, the institution may focus on extensive professional development to help probationary faculty transition to regular status and remain committed to the school. As for length of service, 47 percent were employed 0-3 years followed by 26 percent with 4-8 years of service, and 16 percent over 16 years. The high percentage (47%) with 0-3 years of service aligns with the young age profile. Retaining faculty beyond the first 3-5 years will be critical for the institution.

The findings in Table 2 reveal a generally high job satisfaction among participants emphasizing a moderate level of satisfaction with compensation and benefits (M = 3.36).

Table 2
Summary of Job Satisfaction

Variable	Mean	Interpretation	SD
<i>Compensation and Benefits</i>	3.36	Moderate	0.97
<i>Work Environment</i>	3.85	High	0.83
Total	3.61	High	0.07

The finding is supported by the postulation of Gerhart and Fang (2023) positing the importance of pay where teachers value fair compensation for their work at the most fundamental level, based on their abilities, contributions, and effort (Gerhart & Fang, 2023). Receiving a regular salary is a tangible reward for putting in their effort; hence, this area needs considerable attention from the school administration. Meanwhile, participants, generally, view their work environment very positively as shown in the overall mean of 3.85. Such finding indicates the strong rapport among the teachers which is crucial in their job satisfaction and may ultimately relate to their intention to stay in the institution.

Table 3 shows that teachers reported *high* work-life balance as indicated in the overall mean of 3.92 implying that the teachers can strike a balance between the demands of their work and their tasks at home. Notably, 89 percent of the teachers reported high work balance. This further means that the teachers were not only able to prioritize their work and personal roles in life but also their social, psychological, economic, and mental well-being (Espinosa, 2024).

Table 3
Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Participant's Assessment of Work-life Balance

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Participants
4.51 – 5.0	Very High	3	3.00
3.51 – 4.50	High	89	89.00
2.51 – 3.50	Moderate	8	8.00
1.51 – 2.50	Low	0	0.00

1.0 – 1.50	Very Low	0	0.00
Total		100	100.00
Overall Mean			3.92
Interpretation			High
SD			0.33

Table 4 reflects that as a whole, there is a high engagement of teachers with cognitive engagement as the highest followed by emotional engagement. However, moderate engagement can be detected with physical engagement. This denotes that the teachers' level of determination that they put in exercising their physical duties in school is tending toward a *bearable level* suggesting considerable attention on the end of the school administration. Notably, cognitive engagement got the highest mean (3.82) implying the teacher's understanding of the goals and strategies of the school administration as well as the performance standards matched, (Rivaldo and Nabella, 2023).

Furthermore, emotional engagement was also reported *high* (M=3.59) denoting that the teachers had a high feeling of community at work, motivating them to believe in and support the company's goals and principles, (Astuti, Fitria, & Rohana, 2020). In brief, teachers invested in their emotions and feelings as they performed their multifaceted tasks in the school.

Table 4
Summary of Work Engagement

Variable	Mean	Interpretation	SD
<i>Physical Engagement</i>	3.26	Moderate	0.92
<i>Cognitive Engagement</i>	3.82	High	0.85
<i>Emotional Engagement</i>	3.59	High	0.88
Total	3.56	High	0.03

Table 5 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of participants' intention to stay. The data reveal a moderate intention to stay as supported by the overall mean of 3.24 implying that the participants are neither inclined to stay in school nor inclined to leave. Instead, they are somewhat neutral about their job retention, leaning slightly towards staying. This moderate intention to stay may imply that participants are generally satisfied with their jobs but may also have some concerns that prevent them from being fully committed to staying.

Table 5
Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of Participant's Assessment of Intention to Stay

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Participants
4.51 – 5.0	Very High	5	5.00
3.51 – 4.50	High	29	29.00
2.51 – 3.50	Moderate	48	48.00

1.51 – 2.50	Low	14	14.00
1.0 – 1.50	Very Low	4	4.00
Total		100	100.0
Overall Mean		3.24	
Interpretation		Moderate	
SD		0.79	

Table 6 shows that the test of difference in participants' intention to stay based on age yielded statistically significant results ($p < .000$), indicating substantial variations across different age demographics; hence, the null hypothesis can be rejected. Participants aged 25-34 reported the lowest intention to stay ($M=3.02$). In contrast, those in the 35-44-year-old category demonstrated a higher intention to stay ($M=3.82$). Notably, participants aged 45-64 years exhibited the strongest intention to stay as shown in the mean of 4.15. These findings emphasize a clear age-related disparity in participants' commitment to remaining within their current roles or organizations. The statistical significance reinforces the notion that age plays a significant role in shaping individuals' intentions to stay, likely influenced by factors such as career stability, experience, and evolving professional priorities over time.

Table 6

Result of The Test of Difference in Participants' Intention to Stay Considering Age, Civil Status, Employment, and Length of Service

AGE				F value	p	Effect size
25-34 years old (N=71)	35-44 years old (N=9)	45-64 years old (N=16)	Over 65 years old (N=4)	8.75**	.000	0.52
3.02	3.82	3.69	4.15			
<i>**significant at 0.01 level</i>						
Civil Status			SD	t	p	Effect size
Single (n=71)	Married (n =29)		.788	3.47**	.001	0.764
3.08	3.65		.636			
Employment Status			SD	t	p	Effect size
Regular (n =57)	Probationary (n =43)		.714	3.09**	.003	0.623
3.45	2.97		.808			
Length of Service				F value	p	Effect size
0-2 years (n=44)	3-9 years (n=30)	10-45 years (n=26)		9.02**	.000	0.43
2.10	3.16	3.75				

***significant at 0.01 level*

The test of difference in participants' intention to stay based on civil status, revealed statistically significant results ($p < .001$), highlighting significant differences in commitment across different civil status categories; hence, the null hypothesis can be

rejected. Participants who identified as *single* reported an average intention to stay score of 3.08, while those who identified as *married* had a higher average score of 3.65. This indicates that married participants expressed a stronger intention to stay within their current roles than their single counterparts. The statistical significance at $p < .001$ suggests that civil status plays a significant role in shaping individuals' intentions regarding their professional continuity. Factors such as family responsibilities, stability, and personal priorities associated with marital status may contribute to these distinct levels of commitment to staying in their current employment situations.

Significant differences between various employment categories were observed, as evidenced by statistically significant results ($p < .003$) from the test of the difference in participants' intention to stay based on employment status. With an average score of 3.45, tenured participants expressed a greater intention to stay than those in probationary status, who scored 2.97. This implies that, in contrast to those in probationary roles, people in permanent employment status show a stronger commitment to stay in school. The bearing of participants' goals toward professional continuity is highlighted by the statistical significance at $p < .003$, which highlights this difference. Variables, including job security, stability, and degree of integration within the company, may cause these various levels of commitment between regular and probationary teachers.

The test of difference of participants' length of service on their intention to stay, and the results were highly significant ($p < .000$), indicating notable variations in commitment among the different service length categories. With an average score of 2.10, participants who had served for between one and two years stated they had the least desire to stay. An average of 3.16 indicated that those who had served for three to nine years intended to stay in school. Surprisingly, individuals who had served for between 10 and 45 years on average had the strongest inclination to stay ($M = 3.75$). These results highlight the significant connection between commitment and length of service, with employees with longer tenure indicating a greater desire to stay in their current institutions. The strength of these differences is highlighted by the statistical significance at $p < .000$, which implies that people's intentions regarding professional continuity are considerably influenced by their tenure inside an organization. The various degrees of commitment shown across varying service durations may be attributed to elements like job satisfaction, loyalty, and professional advancement possibilities over time.

The finding aligns with Aboramadan, Albashiti, Alharazin, and Dahleez research (2020) espousing that faculty members exhibit higher commitment and engagement due to their roles, career advancement opportunities, and institutional involvement. Long-serving faculty members may experience increased institutional commitment, but they may also experience burnout or dissatisfaction if not adequately supported or recognized (Boon et al., 2020). Teachers' expectations and priorities according to Palmer et al. (2020) vary across age groups, with younger faculty seeking growth opportunities and a dynamic work environment and older faculty valuing stability and legacy-making. Furthermore, teachers with family commitments often prioritize work-life balance and seek institutions with family-friendly policies, which are more likely to retain them (Okiko, L., 2020). Civil

status likewise impacts faculty social support networks, with a supportive institutional environment that accommodates the needs of single and married faculty members contributing to retention (Abella, 2020).

Table 7 shows that the entire model is significant as indicated by an F-value of 15.99 with a p-value of 0.000. The results denote that participants who reported higher levels of job satisfaction, better work-life balance, and greater work engagement also tended to have a higher intention to stay in their current positions. It implies that factors contributing to a positive work experience, such as feeling satisfied with one's job, having a good balance between work and personal life, and being actively engaged in one's work tasks, play a crucial role in influencing individuals' decisions to remain in their jobs (Jessica, et. al., 2023).

These findings highlight the importance for organizations to focus on creating a work environment that fosters job satisfaction, supports work-life balance, and encourages high levels of engagement among employees. Doing so contributes to teachers' well-being and job satisfaction and enhances their commitment and intention to stay with the organization, ultimately benefiting both the individuals and the organization as a whole. The finding is supported by Nur et al. (2023) espousing that job satisfaction and work-life balance significantly affect the intention to stay, while work-life balance significantly influences organizational commitment.

Table 7. *Regression Analysis of the Influence of Job Satisfaction, Work-Life Balance, and Work Engagement on Participants' Intention to Stay*

	Unstandardized		Standardize	t	Sig.
	Coefficients	Std. Error	d		
	B		Beta		
(Constant)	.757	.943		.803	.424
Job Satisfaction	.381	.139	.273	2.74**	.007
Work-Life Balance	-.280	.209	-.117	-1.34	.184
Work Engagement	.616	.162	.383	3.80**	.000
Model Summary					
R = .577	R ² =.333	Adjusted R ² = .312	F=15.99**	p=.000	

Regression Equation

$$Y (\text{Intention to Stay}) = .757 (\text{Constant}) + .381 (\text{Job Satisfaction}) + -.280 (\text{Work-Life Balance}) + .616 (\text{Work Engagement})$$

However, only 33.3 percent of the variability in their intention to stay can be accounted for by a combination of the independent variables. The remaining 66.7 percent can be attributed to other factors not covered in this study such as organizational culture, career advancement opportunities, leadership styles, workplace relationships, employee recognition and rewards, job autonomy, work flexibility, and external market factors. These additional variables may also significantly influence participants' intention to stay, and further exploration and support from existing literature can provide a more

comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing retention decisions in organizations.

Among the independent variables, work engagement came out as having the highest significant influence on their intention to stay, indicating that for every unit increase in their work engagement, there is a corresponding .616 increase in their intent to stay ($B=.616$, $t= 3.80$, $p = .000$) followed by job satisfaction, which also showed a significant positive impact on participants' intention to stay ($B=.467$, $t= 2.91$, $p=.004$). These results propose that enhancing work engagement and job satisfaction can be key organizational strategies to improve employee retention rates. It is logical to surmise that teachers would find their work very meaningful if they are actively engaged in promoting students' welfare such as facilitating and assisting them in various curricular activities, making them win in contests, and other affairs in the school. Students' manifestation of "successes" as a product of their coaching and support is a fulfilling experience for them; hence, their active engagement will likely turn to their job satisfaction making them increase their intention to stay in the organization. However, other unexplored factors outside the scope of this study, such as organizational culture, career development opportunities, and leadership styles, may also play crucial roles in influencing participants' intention to stay, warranting further investigation and support from the existing research literature.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Primarily, individuals exhibit differing degrees of satisfaction with various factors. For example, work-life balance and the work environment are rated higher than pay perks and physical engagement. Furthermore, the intention of participants to remain is significantly influenced by demographic parameters, including age, marital status, work status, and duration of service. This underscores the intricate relationship between personal and organizational elements in determining degrees of commitment.

Additionally, participants' commitment is collectively influenced by job satisfaction, work-life balance, and work engagement, highlighting the importance of establishing a healthy work atmosphere, encouraging work-life balance, and improving cognitive and emotional engagement to increase employee commitment and retention in the school.

Furthermore, the theoretical framework of this study integrates Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, emphasizing motivators and hygiene factors in job satisfaction is confirmed in the study. Hygiene factors such as pay and benefits are important but on top of all these are the motivating factors that appear long-lasting creating an impact on their intention to stay in the school. The Theory of Planned Behavior also provides a holistic view of factors affecting employees' intentions to stay. It shows that integration underlines the significance of a supportive, engaging work environment in enhancing retention, emphasizing the interplay between intrinsic motivations, job characteristics, work-life balance, and organizational support in shaping employee commitment and satisfaction.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author/s declare that strict adherence to the ethics of research was observed having obtained informed consent from the research participants, that the latter's well-being was safeguarded and their identities were kept anonymous.

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